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USING THE ANDROID EMULATOR FOR THE PEPPER ROBOT FOR PROJECT WORK

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ABSTRACT

Excellence in teaching and learning requires that students acquire practical skills in addition to theoretical knowledge. For this purpose, many modules include term projects. In order to realize the practical projects in times of Covid-19, project topics have to be adapted so that students can work on them exclusively remotely. For classes that convey e.g. the principles of Human-Machine Interaction, one possibility is the use of the android-based emulator for the social robot Pepper. The emulator allows students to practically implement ideas for the Pepper robot without needing access to a laboratory. Thereby comparable options are conceivable for other subject areas. This paper presents a concept for remotely teaching and learning the principles of Human-Machine Interaction. The module is designed in such a way that the students realize their projects within the framework of User Centered Design. In addition to the technical implementation of the ideas using the Pepper Emulation, it is the students' task to determine the needs and requirements of the defined group of users on the basis of online questionnaires and online focus groups. The concept thus makes it possible to ensure a practical experience for students in times of Covid-19. However, the use of remote labs also offers many advantages for students, such as time and location autonomy, which is beneficial to the individualization of learning processes. In the presented paper, a guideline for the design of remote practical work is presented and advantages and disadvantages are discussed based on the experience of the conducted course.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Application-oriented teaching and learning of competencies

Excellence in teaching and learning requires that students acquire practical skills in addition to theoretical knowledge. In recent years, the concept of problem based learning has become more and more prominent in engineering education. Problem based learning is a student-centered pedagogy that makes use of real-world problems as a challenge to enhance and promote student learning [1]. Compared to traditional teacher-centered approaches, problem based learning particularly promotes critical thinking skills, problem solving skills, cognitive skills and overall performance, which is highly desirable in engineering education. One way to integrate problem based learning in higher education are term projects.

Traditionally, term projects are designed to be carried out in university laboratories. Such practice-oriented projects are established in particular in the teaching of universities of applied sciences [2]. The laboratories provide the appropriate infrastructure for practical work. However, with the Covid-19 pandemic, teaching at universities was shifted from face-to-face to online formats, preventing project work from being conducted on-site. New concepts suitable for remote execution were required to continue to conduct practice-oriented, problem based learning challenges as part of courses.

Concepts for remote labs have first been used in the 90's in the context of distance learning to opened up access to experiments to a larger group of students using the new possibilities of the internet [3]. Remote access was a key factor during the Covid-19 Pandemic and worldwide high quality concepts for distance learning were realized. One approach was to record laboratory experiences and put videos, quizzes and data online for students to engage with the material [4]. Others prepared take-home kits for students, gave remote access to real in-lab equipment or provided data to enable students to perform simulations of physical systems [5]. The authors of this study compared different approaches and showed that take-home kits (92 % positive rating) were the best replacement for in-lab activities followed by remote access (82 % positive rating). Using videos and quizzes as replacement was only enjoyed by 57 % of the students. When developing a remote concept, however, in addition to the preferences of students, the availability of resources and the feasibility of implementing the content in accordance with the module also play a decisive role.

1.2 Human-Machine Interaction

Human-Machine Interaction is a cross-disciplinary area (e.g., engineering, psychology, ergonomics, design) that deals with the theory, design, implementation, and evaluation of the ways that humans use and interact with machines [6]. A special form of human-machine interaction is human-robot interaction. Human-robot interaction is concerned with how physically human-like robots interact with humans in the social world and how social robots are perceived as social agents [7]. In order to understand the complexity and possibilities of this humanoid embodiment and to

apply it to the needs of specific target groups, semester-long projects have been designed for the courses Human-Machine Interaction and Design of Anthropomorphic Machines of the Mechanical Engineering program at the Cologne University of Applied Sciences. The methodology will be presented in the next section.

This paper deals with the question of how semester-long problem-based learning challenges can be designed completely remotely. What are the advantages and disadvantages for both students and lecturers? What design recommendations can be made for future, post-covid courses?

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Objective and working environment

The given goal for the students was to develop an application for the Pepper robot for a specific application scenario. The students could choose between four different scenarios: Elementary school, entrance hall of the university, senior living communities and train station. Due to the Covid-19 pandemic, study courses took place online. Therefore, the working environment for the semester-long projects had to be accessible remotely as well. For this reason, a programming environment was selected for the implementation of the projects, which is based on freely available software only. The courses had a scope of 5 ECTS credits. The course Human-Machine Interaction was attended by 45, the course Design of Anthropomorphic Machines by 65 students. They worked on the projects in groups of 3-5 people. For virtual collaboration, the teams were able to use the MS Teams collaboration platform. The grading of the modules was composed of 50% final presentation and 50% documentation of the projects.

2.2 Use of the User Centered Design Framework

Students were assigned to work on the semester-long projects within the User Centered Design framework [8]. An overview of the UCD and the recommended methodological approaches for the phases is given in Fig 1. The framework is highly suitable for developing user-centered products and was thus appropriate for the course Human-Machine Interaction and Design of Anthropomorphic Machines

In the research phase, the students' task was to develop a suitable persona for the application scenario. For this purpose, they were to conduct either interviews or a focus group to determine the needs and requirements of the defined group of users and develop the persona based on the findings.

In the design phase, conceptual and physical design had to be ideated. In the process, activities, actions and goals were developed that were tailored to the application scenario and the persona.

In the develop phase, the students were to implement the developed ideas with the Android Pepper emulator. The programming environment was based on Android Studio, the Pepper SDK as an Android Studio plugin and the Java library QiSDK. Students were able to install the software on their computer.

In the evaluation phase, the goal was to test the applications using either (online) surveys, user tests or focus groups. The evaluation could be performed using video material. Based on the feedback, students were asked to give an outlook on which next steps they would recommend for the project. Students were further encouraged to incorporate evaluations into all phases of the UCD, but it was only mandatory after the develop phase.

Fig. 1. Recommended methodological approaches for the individual phases of the UCD

The concept of UCD envisions multiple cycles of the process for optimal product development. Due to the time constraints of the semester-long projects, the students only performed one cycle. Based on the results of the evaluation phase, they had to provide an outlook on which steps would now be suitable for the further development of the project.

2.3 Procedure of the semester

At the beginning of the semester, the contents and objectives of the course were presented. The topics for the semester-long projects were also presented here. Based on the students' topic preferences, the groups were allocated. In the following four events, a winter or summer school took place, which familiarized the students with the programming environment in a targeted manner. Thus, the influence of previous experiences with programming which differed between students could be minimized. The following six events were divided into two sessions of 45 minutes each. In the first 45 minutes, students received input on relevant topics such as artificial intelligence, social agents, navigation and control, and computer vision. In the second 45 minutes, further exercises were carried out which supported the progress of the projects. Content-related and technical questions concerning the projects were discussed. In particular, students had the opportunity to receive assistance on problems related to the definition of the persona and the implementation of the envisioned applications. Students were only given the dates of the final presentations as deadlines for completing the projects. No milestones such as the completion of the persona were specified.

3 RESULTS

This paper presents a concept for the remote execution of a problem-based learning challenge in the context of semester-long projects to improve learning outcomes for the courses Human-Machine Interaction and Design of Anthropomorphic Machines. By going through the UCD process, students learned the importance of involving the relevant target group and gained hands-on experience implementing robotic applications. The understanding of the theoretical contents of the lecture could be deepened by the addition of remotely conducted semester-long projects. The groups were able to successfully set up the programming environment and implement viable applications for the Pepper robot. The Pepper robot and sample code is illustrated in Fig 2. The implementation of the applications promoted the application and deepening of programming knowledge. The concept thus makes it possible to ensure a practical experience for students in times of Covid-19. A guideline for the design of remote practical work is presented and the advantages and disadvantages of the concept as experienced are discussed in the following sections. Subsequently, effects on the learning process are discussed.

Fig. 2. Illustration of the Pepper robot and sample code

3.1 Guideline for the design of remote practical work

In this section a guideline for the design of remote practical work is presented. It is assumed that the subject of the lecture is given. In the next step, a suitable problem based challenge must be defined. The challenge should be based on real world problems. This makes the relevance of the challenge prominent, which has a positive effect on the motivation of students [9] [10] [11]. Particularly suitable are specific social challenges or distinct research questions from ongoing projects. Challenge selection must also take into account the scope of the semester-long project so that students are able to complete the assignment in the time frame provided. Based on the topic of the challenge, a suitable methodological framework must be given on the one hand, on the basis of which the students are to solve the challenge. Through the framework, the required methodical approach is made

concrete and the solution process is guided and supported appropriately. On the other hand, a working environment must be defined, which is suitable for solving the challenge and which has to be accessible remotely for all students.

Fig. 3. Illustration of the guideline for the design of remote practical work

3.2 Advantages and disadvantages of using remote labs

The use of remote labs offers many advantages for students. By using the collaborative platform MS Teams, the students were able to organize the teamwork flexibly. Likewise, they were able to design the development of the applications for the Pepper robot independently of the opening hours of the university's laboratories. Through the use of freely accessible software, the students were able to work independently in terms of time and space.

However, several disadvantages of the concept were also experienced during the semester. In the research phase, the conduct of interviews or focus groups was limited. For example, for the scenarios train station or entrance hall university, it would have been desirable to conduct spontaneous interviews in the respective physical environment. Unfortunately, this was not possible due to the Covid-19 restrictions. In the development phase, the development of applications was limited due to the Pepper Android emulator. The emulator allows the development of dialogues and applications for the included tablet. But the robot's movements cannot be manipulated. In the evaluation phase, no real interactions with the Pepper robot could be tested. Although the emulator allows the development of new applications, the testing of these is limited. For example, requests can only be entered via text and aspects such as speech understanding cannot be captured remotely. To mitigate these disadvantages, test dates have been provided. The lecturers of the module implemented the developed code in the lab on the Pepper robot and the students were given the opportunity to experience their application via video call on the real robot.

3.3 Effects on the learning process

Problem based learning allows to compensate different previous knowledge between students and especially deficits within groups [12] [13]. The combination of problem-

based learning with a remote way of working thus has many advantages for the individualization of learning processes. The design of remote labs allows students to organize the completion of projects according to individual preferences. In addition to the time allocation, the working environment in particular can be freely chosen.

The evaluation of the course showed that the students found the task interesting, practice-oriented and useful. In particular, it was positively noted that the application scenario of the Pepper robot could be freely selected and thus individual interests were taken into account. However, some of the students found the high degree of freedom in designing the application to be problematic and would have liked clearer guidelines for fulfilling the task.

Students were required to set up the programming environment on their own laptops. This allowed the students to invest more or less time in the implementation of the project work according to their respective level of knowledge without being bound by external capacities such as lab time. Some students had hardware problems, which is why alternative solutions had to be provided during the semester in the form of remote access to laboratory computers. The limited resources for remote access made it more challenging for some groups to complete the task. In future, the technical requirements should therefore be checked at the beginning of the semester in order to avoid delays and capacity bottlenecks.

The support from the lecturing team was provided flexibly. Students were able to ask for support throughout the project via the collaboration platform. Compared to face-to-face tutorials, this support was significantly more time-consuming. Problems were not only solved by the lecturing team, but students were able to support each other via the platform. The platform thus also encouraged peer learning.

However, the negative sides of the constraints imposed by the Covid-19 pandemic were also evident in relation to the learning process. Students were able to work remotely, but the living situation of many students does not provide the optimal working environment. Therefore, many students would prefer to work on projects on-site at the university premises. For the future, the use of hybrid concepts is recommended. The advantages of remote concepts, in particular the use of the emulator and the collaboration platform, can be used and supplemented by suitable presence components.

4 SUMMARY

The presented concept demonstrates the chances to realize a successful remote learning process also for practical skills. Besides the selection of a valid problem based learning challenge, the selection of a suitable methodological framework and a suitable working environment is crucial. In post-pandemic times, remote elements should definitely continue to be used, as they can favourably influence the learning process. However, it can be assumed that the learning success of the students is positively influenced by face-to-face meetings through the direct interaction with peers and the efficient, parallel support in case of problems by the lecturers. Further analyses of students' learning conditions are necessary here.

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